

Image-Based Bearing Fault Detection in 3-Phase Induction Motors with Markov Transition Field

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ABSTRACT

Reliable bearing fault diagnosis plays a pivotal role in the maintenance and performance of rotating machinery within industrial settings. This paper presents a novel approach to bearing fault detection, utilizing image processing through Markov Transition Field (MTF). By analyzing time-series current signals, the MTF method converts 1-D data into 2-D images, capturing the transition probabilities of signal patterns over time. This transformation preserves the dynamic characteristics of the signal, facilitating enhanced feature extraction for fault detection. Experimental tests, including fault scenarios in bearings and varying load conditions, demonstrate the method's strong potential for accurate fault classification. Additionally, the MTF-based approach offers a robust, data-driven framework that is resilient to noise and adaptable to different operational environments. This work highlights the significant potential of MTF in predictive maintenance, offering a tool that improves fault detection, reduces downtime, and ensures the reliable operation of mechanical systems.

KEYWORDS: *Induction motor, Markov transition field (MTF), Bearing fault diagnosis, Time-series data, Image processing.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Motor bearings are vital components in rotating systems, playing a crucial role in ensuring the operational efficiency and reliability of various industries, including manufacturing and energy generation. Due to constant operational stress, these bearings experience wear and tear, which can lead to faults that may cause system failures, unscheduled downtimes, and considerable financial losses. Therefore, early detection of bearing faults is essential to minimize risks and maintain smooth operations. Traditional fault detection methods, such as vibration analysis, spectral analysis, and time-domain feature extraction, have been widely used for fault diagnosis. However, these techniques often encounter difficulties when detecting subtle or intricate fault patterns, particularly in noisy or dynamic operational environments. In recent years, data-driven approaches have gained traction in fault diagnosis due to their capability to identify hidden patterns in large datasets.

Over the years, a range of methods have been proposed for the detection and classification of motor faults, including bearing failures, rotor bar defects (Mishra et al.,2025), etc. Traditional approaches like stator current analysis (liu et al.,2024), vibration analysis (liu et al.,2024), etc. have been widely utilized, though they often require sophisticated setups and expert interpretation. Machine learning and deep learning models, including support vector machines (SVM) (Han et al.,2021), neural networks (NN) and convolutional neural networks (CNN) (Resendiz-Ochoa E et al.,2021), etc. have proven effective in automatic fault detection and enhancing diagnostic accuracy. Image-based methods like Spectrogram (Aimer et al.,2015), Recurrence plot (Das et al.,2023, Scalogram (Yan et al.,2022), Gramian Angular Field (GAF) and Markov Transition Field (MTF) (Han et al.,2021), etc. have also become increasingly popular, transforming time-series data into image representations that can be analyzed using computer vision techniques for more robust fault classification.

After thoroughly reviewing existing research, it is evident that many studies rely on stator current, vibration and acoustic signals to detect and diagnose faults effectively. Additionally, recent studies have focused on fault diagnosis using specific signal conditioning techniques, analyzing the frequency spectrum of line current to identify various bearing faults (inner race and outer race faults). Building on this, the

objective of the present study is to develop a reliable and effective method for diagnosing motor bearing faults, with an emphasis on detecting the inner race bearing faults in induction motors by analyzing the stator currents. This research investigates the application of the Markov Transition Field technique for bearing fault detection, with a focus on its ability to capture both temporal and spatial relationships within stator current data. Through this study, the author aims to contribute to the expanding field of predictive maintenance by offering a more accurate, efficient, and data-driven approach for detecting bearing faults, ultimately improving the reliability and performance of industrial machinery.

2. SCOPE OF THE WORK

To accomplish the objective, first, three phase stator current data were acquired with the help of a customized experimental setup that was built under controlled laboratory environment. The inner race of the bearing was deliberately cracked to emulate faults in the bearing of the motor. Two operating cases i.e. motor with healthy and faulty bearing were considered for the current scope of study. Experiments were also conducted on variable load conditions so that the proposed fault diagnosis method becomes load independent. After acquiring the three phase time series current data at all operating cases, the 1-D current data of each phase were converted into 2-D images using MTF technique. By converting time-series data into 2D images, it enables the use of advanced image classification techniques, making it a valuable tool for enhancing accuracy, supporting real-time performance, and enabling automated decision-making. Upon close investigation on all MTF images significant changes could be observed due to change in operating cases which in turn helps to differentiate the healthy cases from the faulty cases.

3. METHOD

3.1 Experimental Arrangement

To collect the 3-phase stator current data, experiments were carried out using a 2hp, 320V, 3-phase star-connected induction motor. A bearing with an inner race fault was integrated into the motor to evaluate its performance under fault conditions. To simulate variable load conditions, the induction motor was mechanically coupled to a DC generator that powers lamp loads. Three single-phase autotransformers, each with a voltage adjustment range of 0% to 125%, were placed between the power source and the motor, ensuring a stable three-phase voltage supply to the motor despite any supply voltage fluctuations. For current signal acquisition, a PC was connected to a YOKOGAWA 3-phase digital power meter. The photograph of the experimental setup and its schematic diagram are shown in Figure 1(a) and 1(b), respectively.

Figure 1. Picture of experimental set-up (a) and schematic diagram (b).

This study investigates two motor operating conditions: one with a healthy bearing and the other with a fault in the inner race of the bearing. The picture of the faulted bearing used in experiment has been shown in Figure 2. Experiments were performed under two different load conditions, specifically at 0% and 25% of full load, to assess the performance of the proposed approach under varying load levels. A summary of the operating conditions and their corresponding identifiers is presented in Table 1.

Figure 2. Picture of bearing with crack in inner-race

Table 1. Case studies along with their identifiers.

Sl no.	Case identifiers	Case Description
1	H_NL	Motor with healthy bearing and 0% of full load
2	H_L1	Motor with healthy bearing and 25% of full load
3	IR_NL	Motor with faulty bearing and 0% of full load
4	IR_L1	Motor with faulty bearing and 25% of full load

3.2 Background theory of Markov Transition Field (MTF)

The MTF (Han et al., 21) offers a novel way to represent the temporal evolution of signals within a probabilistic framework. This method is grounded in the concept of Markov chains, where system state transitions over time are modelled and visualized as a field. By converting time-series data into discrete states, the MTF captures the dynamic behaviour of bearing faults and creates a representation that enhances pattern recognition and fault classification. The core of the Markov Transition Field (MTF) lies in the concept of a Markov chain. A Markov chain is a mathematical framework that models a system as a sequence of states, where the transition from one state to another depends only on the current state, not on the previous states. This property, called the Markov property, simplifies the modeling process by making future states conditionally independent of past states once the present state is known. In the context of time-series data, this model is used to represent how the system evolves over time, where the continuous time-series is discretized into a sequence of discrete states.

The process of transforming continuous time-series data into an image involves the following steps:

1. **Discretizing Time-Series Data:** The first step involves converting the continuous time-series data into discrete states. This is achieved through methods like state quantization, which maps continuous values into predefined intervals or bins, making the data suitable for Markov chain modeling.

2. **Markov Chain Representation:** After discretizing the data, the transitions between these states are tracked across time. A transition matrix is constructed to capture the probability of transitioning from one state to another between consecutive time steps. This matrix forms the backbone of the Markov chain representation.

3. Building the Markov Transition Field (MTF): The transition matrix is used to create the MTF, which is represented as a 2D image. Each pixel in this image corresponds to a state transition, with pixel intensity representing the probability of transitioning between two states. This visual representation encodes both the temporal and spatial relationships of the system's dynamics, providing a comprehensive view of how the system evolves over time.

A time series $X = (x_1, x_2, x_3 \dots x_n)$ can be analysed by dividing its range of values into Q intervals. Each element x_i is then assigned to a corresponding interval q_j . This allows the creation of a $Q \times Q$ matrix W , where w_{ij} represents the probability that an element in interval j is followed by an element in interval i . The sum of probabilities for each interval j equals 1. While W acts as a Markov transition matrix, it does not fully capture the characteristics of the original time series X due to information loss and weak dependence on the distribution of X . Therefore, W needs improvement. The improved Markov transition matrix M , with cells M_{ij} is defined as:

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} w_{ij} | x_1 \in q_i, x_1 \in q_j & \dots & \dots & w_{ij} | x_1 \in q_i, x_n \in q_j \\ w_{ij} | x_2 \in q_i, x_1 \in q_j & \dots & \dots & w_{ij} | x_2 \in q_i, x_n \in q_j \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ w_{ij} | x_n \in q_i, x_1 \in q_j & \dots & \dots & w_{ij} | x_n \in q_i, x_n \in q_j \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Initially, 3-phase current signals were captured for both motor operating conditions i.e. healthy and the inner race (IR) fault. Once the current data was collected, each set of current signals was normalized by referencing the peak value of the corresponding phase currents recorded during the H_NL condition. This normalization ensures that any variations in current amplitude due to load changes or other external factors do not interfere with the fault detection process. Figure 3 (a) and 3(b) represent the 3-phase normalized current waveforms obtained at H_NL and IR_NL conditions, respectively. Whereas, the current waveforms of H_L1 and IR_L1 conditions have been shown in Figure 4(a) and 4(b), respectively.

Figure 3. 3-phase current signals obtained at (a) H_NL and (b) IR_NL conditions

Figure 4. 3-phase current signals obtained at (a) H_L1 and (b) IR_L1 conditions

Following a basic visual inspection of the current waveforms, no significant alterations were evident when the operating conditions were changed. That is why the time series data of each phase current signals were converted into 2-D images by the MTF. Images obtained from the 3-phase current signals under both healthy and IR fault conditions of the motor through MTF have been shown in the Figure 5 to 8.

Figure 5. MTF images of (a) R-phase, (b) Y-phase and (c) B-phase current signals obtained at H_NL condition

Figure 6. MTF images of (a) R-phase, (b) Y-phase and (c) B-phase current signals obtained at IR_NL condition

Figure 7. MTF images of (a) R-phase, (b) Y-phase and (c) B-phase current signals obtained at H_LI condition

Figure 8. MTF images of (a) R-phase, (b) Y-phase and (c) B-phase current signals obtained at IR_LI condition

From Figure 5 to 8 the following observations could be noted:

- The patterns of the MTF images for the same operating case remain largely unchanged, even with variations in the load condition. For instance, the R, Y, and B-phase MTF images for H_NL and H_L1 appear almost identical.
- However, when the operating condition shifts from healthy to faulty, noticeable changes appear in the pattern of the MTF images. Specifically, the red boxes from the 3rd to the 8th in the middle section of the MTF images appear significantly brighter in the healthy condition compared to the inner race fault case. To further illustrate this, the transition probability values (diagonal elements of the transition matrix) derived under the H_NL and IR_NL conditions are presented in Table 2. The transition probabilities under the IR condition are generally higher than those observed under healthy conditions. These values show significant variations as the motor condition changes, indicating that these diagonal transition probabilities could serve as valuable features for fault classification.

Table 2. List of diagonal transition probabilities

Elements of Transition matrix	Transition probability value	
	H_NL	IR_NL
W_{33}	0.857142857	0.894736842
W_{44}	0.852352941	0.890967742
W_{55}	0.846153846	0.863636364
W_{66}	0.857142857	0.869565217
W_{77}	0.858787879	0.866666667
W_{88}	0.862068966	0.913043478

Consequently, it can be concluded that the images produced by the MTF technique offer substantial potential as features to serve as input for a suitable classifier in classifying different motor fault scenarios.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates the successful application of the Markov Transition Field (MTF) technique for bearing fault diagnosis, proving that it offers a more effective and robust alternative to conventional methods. By transforming 3-phase current signals into image representations, MTF extracts complex features crucial for fault detection. The results suggest that MTF-derived images possess significant potential as features for input into a classifier for accurately identifying various motor fault conditions. This project contributes to the development of advanced diagnostic tools, which can improve the accuracy and efficiency of predictive maintenance for motor bearings.

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